

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing

Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Measurement of the Impulse Response of the Guitar to Extract Timbre Features

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Supervisor: Jorge Fuentes

Co-supervisor: Xavier Serra

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Abstract

Nowadays, the guitar is one of the most popular musical instruments all over the world. We can find a great number of models with a wide range of acoustic quality, depending on the way the guitar has been built. The guitar luthiers need to know how to control certain acoustic attributes depending on the type of instrument they want to make. Currently, most luthiers check these acoustic features by analysing the vibration modes and trying to tune them to certain frequencies. To analyse these modes, one of the most used techniques is to analyse the spectrum of the impulsive response by recording a guitar tapped just below its bridge. Although the vibration modes are very important for the final sound of the guitar, there are many more elements that affect the different characteristics that compose the timbre.

In this master thesis, developed in the context of the company MIIL–Musical Instruments Innovation Lab, we have created a computing tool named GIRAS-Guitar Impulse Response Analysis Software. This software allows us to record impulsive responses of guitars, using the technique explained above, and analyse them to obtain new acoustic parameters in addition to the vibration modes, with the aim that these can be used to define the timbre of the instrument. The acoustic parameters we have extracted from the impulsive response have been: the vibration modes, attack time, decay time, vibration sensitivity, centroid, low-to-high frequency ratio and MFCC. To verify if all these computations are related to any timbre feature of the guitar, a small experiment has been made using 5 classical guitars and 4 guitarists, where each of the guitarists had to evaluate the timbre of the guitars according to certain characteristics such as attack, sustain, intelligibility, warmth, balance, volume and dynamic range. After measuring these 5 guitars with our programme, the results are that there are some parameters such as the vibration modes, the attack time, the decay time and the low-to-high frequency ratio, which are clear about their influence on the timbre, and others in which a deeper research and an improvement of the methodology followed is needed to know if they can help to describe the timbre. The most important conclusion of this project is that we have created a software that makes much easier the research on the guitar timber.

Keywords: Guitar; Timbre; Impulse Response; Vibration Modes; MIIL; MuseWaves;

1. Introduction

Guitars are one of the most popular instruments nowadays. There are many kinds of guitars and a great variety of models for each of them. There are many features that allow us to differentiate between different models, but the most important for any musical instrument is the timbre, which can be defined as the frequency content and the spectral profile of the sound [1]. To achieve a specific timbre for a specific guitar model and be able to differentiate it from the rest of models, guitar manufacturers or luthiers must understand certain acoustic proprieties. When designing a product, they need to know how the physical and structural properties of the guitar will affect the final sound.

Most luthiers have learned to design instruments in a very traditional and unscientific way, based more on experience than on physics. Over time, certain physical parameters have been established as standard parameters for the guitar, and most manufacturers try to adjust them to obtain good results. Making sure that the guitars manufactured fit the standard parameters mentioned above, will be essential for the quality of the guitar. For this reason, the methodology followed to measure these parameters will be very important in the design of the guitar.

This master thesis has been developed in collaboration with the company MIIL–Musical Instruments Innovation Lab, which is engaged in the manufacture of musical instruments with new materials such as carbon fiber. This project has been carried out inside the company with the close supervision of Jorge Fuentes, Chief Strategy and Scientific Officer (CSO) and expert engineer in acoustics and vibration, and David Vidal, Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and renown luthier. The purpose of MIIL with this collaboration, is to improve the acoustic design process of its instruments under the brand MuseWaves¹, and especially to better understand the behaviour of the guitar before making the leap to its manufacture with composite materials. The main objective is the development of a software that allows to carry out a spectral analysis of the guitar that helps to define the timbre characteristics of different guitar models. This tool is intended to facilitate to MIIL the process of interpreting the spectral graphs of the impulse response

¹ <https://musewaves.com/>

of the guitars, and therefore, improve the guitar design and help to better understand how the physical and structural properties of the guitar affects the timbre of the instrument.

In addition to the design of the software, this project we will research how certain parameters obtained from the impulsive response can be related to the more subjective terms with which the timbre of the guitar is usually described. The long-term goal is to be able to know how the structural properties of the guitar affect the spectrum of the impulsive response and at the same time how it affects the timbre perceived by the users and by the audience.

2. Background and State of the Art

2.1. Vibration Modes of the Guitar

Once the vibration of the guitar strings is transmitted to the bridge, the sound is generated by the movement of the surfaces that form the body of the guitar. To have good sounds, the guitar has particular ways of vibrating that help to obtain them. These ways the plates are moved are called vibration modes. The different vibration modes are characterized by the way in which the vibrations are distributed across the surface, there will be areas where the vibration is minimal (nodes) and areas where the vibration is maximum (antinodes). There are some frequencies at which the vibration modes have maximum amplitude, and therefore, the sound produced is louder. These frequencies are the resonant frequencies, and the vibration modes at these frequencies are called resonant modes or normal modes. If we observe a graph of the frequency response of a guitar, we will observe that the greatest peaks correspond exactly to the frequencies at which these vibration modes appear. These modes are the ones that define the sound of a guitar, and they have to appear in a specific frequency range to sound like that. In addition, differences between different types or models of guitars are mainly explained by differences between the size, shape, amplitude and resonant frequency of the different modes [2]. This is why a good measurement of resonance modes is one of the most important parts when designing and building a guitar, as these will define the resulting sound and therefore its quality.

In the guitar there are three main resonance frequencies that affect the sound the most, and therefore these will be the ones we are most interested in identifying. These three frequencies correspond to the resonance mode of the top plate of the guitar or soundboard, to the back plate, and to the one produced by the coupling between both surfaces, the resonance frequency of the resonance box. This last frequency is also called “air mode”.

2.2. Vibration Modes Measurement Methods

The most traditional and ancient way to measure the resonant modes of the guitar body is tapping with the fingers or a hammer certain areas of the plates to excite a specific mode and, listening to the sound produced by the tap, try to detect which frequency or note is

the most resonating. Of course, this technique depended a lot on the luthier's ability to detect notes and know where tapping the plates.

Over the years, new techniques have been appearing, allowing the measurement of vibration modes in a more controllable and accurate way. The Chladni patterns method [3] is one of the oldest techniques, which has been evolving in methods such as the holographic interferometry [4] or other more recent and innovative as the use of ultrasound [5]. The Chladni patterns allow to see visually the shape of the modes that the surface has when vibrating at a certain frequency. An interesting and very popular technique in recent years in the field of acoustics is the development of very realistic computer simulations using the finite elements method [6], which in the case of the guitar allow to show graphs of the movement of the plates at a specific frequency. The problem with all these methods that are not related to the audio processing, is that most of them require very advanced and expensive technology, and high knowledge about the used tools to be able to make the measurements.

If we focus on the methods that use audio processing to measure the vibration modes of string instruments bodies, we will observe that most of the researches carried out use the technique known as “tapping”. This technique consists mainly of recording the different taps that were made around the body of the guitar in the most traditional method, and record them with a microphone to extract as much information as possible using digital signal processing. We can divide this process into two parts, the recording and the processing part.

For the realization of impulses, most researches use an impulse hammer that is usually used manually. When tapping is made manually, it is difficult to control the energy with which each tap is made, and each sound response will result in a different amplitude. To avoid this problem, several taps are recorded, and an average of all signals is made. It is also common the use of force sensors coupled to the hammer that allow to know exactly the force that has been applied in each tap. Condenser microphones are normally used for recording, placed perpendicularly about one metre from the soundboard, but other configurations may also be possible. Cook, P. and Trueman, D. place the guitar inside an icosahedron with 12 cardioid microphones, one at each vertex, so in addition to the

frequency response to the impulse, they will be able to obtain information about the directivity of the guitar [7].

Once the impulsive signal is obtained, it has to be processed in order to compute the current vibration modes. Most of the work carried out in this field is based on Fourier transforms to obtain the signal spectrum. Erkut, C., Tolonen, T., Karjalainen, M. & Välimäki, V. developed a software that represented in a 3D graph, the frequency response to the impulse over time of a Turkish tanbur [8], using 4096 point FFT's and a 25 per cent overlapping Hanning window of 2.31 milliseconds. The representation is made where the relevant information can be found, up to 1000 Hz on the frequency axis and up to 18 milliseconds on the time axis.

Farina, A., Langhoff, A. & Tronchin, L. propose two ways of measuring impulsive response in violins [9], a direct method and a reciprocal method. They use MLS (Maximum Length Sequence) signals to obtain high accuracy impulse responses. This method allows to compute the cross-correlation between the input signals and the output of a linear system. The direct method is still based on the tapping technique, with the difference that the measurements are taken inside an anechoic chamber and the taps are made by a force transducer fed with the MLS signal. The signal recorded is cross-correlated with the original one to obtain the impulse response. The reciprocal method is based on vibrating the violin with an MLS signal that is emitted by a loudspeaker inside the anechoic chamber and which radiates a frequency ramp. The vibrations of the violin are captured by a phonograph needle on the bridge, whose electrical output is cross-correlated with the loudspeaker signal. The authors obtain much better results for the direct method than for the reciprocal one, which introduces a lot of noise due to the loudspeaker and the phonograph needle.

A more modern and accurate way to measure the frequency response of the guitar is the use of shakers to excite the guitar in the desired way. These devices allow to insert any type of signal previously configured by means of vibrations directly in the body of the guitar by means of a stick adhered to the bridge. Lee, N., Chaigne, A., Smith, J. and Arcas, K. measured the behaviour of the gypsy guitar placing the guitar on the floor of an anechoic chamber, exciting the bridge with a shaker producing white noise, and measuring the resulting sound with a condenser microphone placed above the instrument

[10]. Brasov, U. T. analysed the Chladni patterns produced in different classical guitar bodies by exciting the soundboard with a shaker at frequencies at which strings are normally tuned [11]. The problem of this technique is the high cost of the shaker technology.

To conclude, Stoppani, G. has developed a number of applications for modal analysis that have been used mainly in researches on stringed instruments [12][13]. Some of these applications contain several features that may be interesting for the development of our own software. Some of the features these applications allow to do are capturing frequency response, estimating mode parameters, plotting mode shapes, viewing animations, comparing different data and doing all sorts of averaging [14].

2.3. Impulse Response Features

Once we have the impulsive response of the guitar, we need to analyse it to obtain parameters that make it easier to interpret the spectrum. All these parameters have been decided according to the needs of the MIIL company when analysing the impulsive response of a guitar. We can obtain data from both the time domain and the frequency domain.

In the time domain we can obtain two values, those corresponding to the attack and to the decay of the impulsive response. Attack refers to the time the impulsive signal takes to reach its maximum amplitude, and decay refers to the time it takes to decrease a certain amplitude threshold. Studies made up to this date about the attack are more related to how the strings are excited than to the attack of the impulsive response of the guitar body [15]. However, it is possible that this parameter also influences the final sound of the guitar, so it can be interesting to compute it. Regarding decay, Boullosa, R. R. measured the Early Decay Time (EDT) of three different guitars made of different woods [16]. The EDT is defined as the time the signal needs to decay 10 dB from its maximum, and sometimes is multiplied by six to get the value of Reverberation Time normally used in acoustic (time in decay 60 dB).

If we focus on the frequency domain, apart from the three main resonance modes of which we have spoken previously, we can calculate other parameters that can have a significant

importance in the guitar's timbre. One of the parameters that surely influence the timbre of the instrument, and that can be easily observed in the spectrograms, is the bandwidth of the resonant peaks. The width of the peak is usually related to how easy it is for that structure to vibrate at that frequency. The wider a peak is, the more the structure tends to vibrate at that frequency. Jansson, E. call this propriety as vibration sensitivity and calculate it with the following formula (*figure 1*) [17]:

$$VS = PV - 20 \log \frac{RF}{B}$$

VS = Vibration Sensitivity (dB)
PV = Peak Value (dB)
RF = Resonant Frequencies (Hz)
B = Bandwidth 3 dB Below the Peak (Hz)

Figure 1: Vibration sensitivity formula by Jansson, E.

If we analyse the distribution of energy across the spectrum, we can calculate if one frequency response has more low or high frequency content than another. There are two parameters that can be useful in our project, the centroid and the low-to-high frequency ratio. The centroid calculates the frequency that divides a range of frequencies into two parts with equal amount of energy on each side. This value is widely used to know around which frequencies the energy is distributed. Schubert, E., Wolfe, J. & Tarnopolsky, A. analysed the relationship between the timbre brightness of multiple instruments and the centroid of notes played with them [18]. The low-to-high frequency ratio represents the relationship between the energy contained in low frequency and that contained in high frequency. It is calculated by dividing the absolute energy of the whole spectrum for low frequencies by the energy at high frequencies (LF/HF), according to a frequency established as the limit between low and high frequencies. One of the areas where this parameter has already been used is in heart rate variability analysis [19].

To conclude, one last analysis that can give us a lot of information is to calculate the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC). This set of parameters gives us information about the spectral differences between the different frames in which the frequency response is analysed [20]. The MFCC calculation is based on the way humans perceive

sound. These values are normally used in voice recognition, because it is very useful for analysing formants, and in recent years, in many musical applications that use machine learning. Dosenbach, K., Fohl, W. & Meisel, A. developed a machine learning algorithm that differentiated between three models of guitars with 80% accuracy using MFCC as features to train the algorithm [21]. With these parameters it is possible to come to some conclusion about more ambiguous characteristics of the guitar's timbre, which at first sight cannot be related to any frequency characteristic.

2.4. Guitar descriptors commonly used

In spite of an analysis of impulsive response can be really useful, it is also necessary to know the terms commonly used by guitarists to describe a guitar. It is necessary to know the words that are really used when a guitarist tests a guitar, and we have to try to find a theoretical meaning to those attributes. Knowing which terms are normally used in the guitar world is quite a complex task, as these are very subjective descriptions, and each person has a different way of naming the same things. In addition, how you appreciate a guitar characteristic depends on many more factors such as language, the part of the world you are in, the type of sounds you are used to hearing, the level of musical education, and so on. Traube, C. made a very complete study of the guitar timbre, which also includes a very advanced analysis of the verbal descriptors for the timbre of the classical guitar [22]. She conducted an experiment with 22 guitarists who were asked to choose the 10 adjectives that best define a guitar, coming to compile a total of 108 adjectives, of which was also requested a description and the way to perceive them. However, the adjectives compiled in that research are all very subjective and very emotional. There is a list of characteristics that are normally used to try to describe the guitar in a more objective way. Some of these features, that may be useful for our research, are the following:

- **Attack:** The sensation of the time it takes for a note to reach maximum volume after plucking the string.
- **Sustain:** Sensation related to the duration of a note on a guitar after plucking it.
- **Intelligibility:** Level of clarity with which a note can be perceived and distinguished when the string is sounding.

- Warmness: This parameter is one of the most subjective and aims to measure the frequency content of a sound in a very general way. This value is higher if in the guitar timbre can be appreciated more low frequencies content than high ones, and lower if it happens the other way around.
- Balance: Refers to the tonal difference between the different notes along the fretboard. A guitar is more balanced the less difference there is between the timbre of the low and high notes.
- Volume: Loudness of the instrument according to the perception of the guitarist while playing. Many times the perception is not the same for the person who is playing and for those who are listening, due to the directivity of the guitar and the acoustics of the room where it is played. The loudness of the guitar perceived at a certain distance from the one playing it is commonly called projection.
- Dynamic Range: This is the difference of volume between soft and loud sounds. When an instrument has a high dynamic range it means that there is a lot of difference between the softest sound you can produce and the loudest sound.

Although these parameters are intended to evaluate very clear features, these parameters are often interpreted differently or confused with others. In addition, the way each person plays the guitar to try to evaluate these attributes can be completely different. This is the main reason why it is necessary to establish some parameters that calculate certain physical properties that allow us to evaluate the guitars in a more objective way, avoiding confusions.

3. Methodology

The development of this project has consisted mainly in the creation of a software that calculates theoretical parameters of the impulse response signal of a guitar already assembled. This programme has been developed using Matlab and Matlab's app designer tool for the interface, and we have assigned it the name GIRAS-Guitar Impulse Response Analysis Software. Once this programme has been elaborated, a small experiment has been carried out to try to reach some conclusions about which parameters extracted from the impulsive response influence the final sound of the guitar when a musician plays it.

Finally, the method chosen to perform the analysis is the “tapping” technique, mainly due to the low cost of materials required to apply this technique and how easy it is to obtain the impulsive response, without the need of high technical knowledge. In addition, the processing of the signals obtained in this way is quite flexible. By using this technique, the analysis can be progressively improved by adding more advanced technology without the need to make significant changes in the signal processing part.

The developed experiment can be divided into the following steps:

- Recording with GIRAS of impulsive responses tapping near the bridge of five classical guitars already built and in use.
- Calculation with GIRAS of the characteristics of the recorded signal that may be related to the timbre of the guitar.
- Conducting a survey where guitarists evaluate the timbre of the guitars analysed in a more personal way.
- Comparison of the data computed with GIRAS with the survey data in order to find some relationship between them, and be able to conclude if any of the computed parameters is directly related to a guitar timbre quality.

In the following sub-sections, we will define in detail how each of the steps have been carried out. The design and operation of GIRAS will be explained in more detail in section 4. The results of both the software and the survey, and the comparison between the two, can be seen in section 5.

3.1. Recording Method

First of all, we have to explain that the recording of impulsive responses is done in real time by GIRAS, at the same time as the parameters are being calculated. The final impulsive response to be analysed is obtained by computing the arithmetic mean of a number of impulsive responses of the taps carried out according to the number of taps pre-set in the programme (ten by default). This average is made to try to counteract the differences between each tap, since in this experiment we cannot control neither the force with which the impact is made nor the exact position where tapping is made, factors that will vary the response of each of the taps. In addition, after the mean, the resulting signal is normalized to the maximum amplitude of the impulse with the greatest amplitude. This is done to be able to compare the responses of different guitars without considering the amplitude. The more similar is the force with which the different taps are made to analyse the same guitar, the amplitude of the maximum peak will be closer to one. By calculating in real time, we can observe in the programme how the form of the frequency response to the impulse becomes more stable as more taps are made and the mean is made of a greater number of signals. In addition, using the individual spectrums tool of GIRAS, we can see in *figure 2* the spectrum of each of the taps and how consistent is the shape of this.

Figure 2: Individual spectrums of each of the taps made on one of the guitars used in the experiment

Knowing the limitations of the recording model proposed, it is necessary to make a set up that minimizes the differences between the different impulses to record. In addition, in order to obtain the most accurate results possible, it is also necessary to use suitable microphones to record impulsive response sounds. The model must help to ensure that the analysis is completely reproducible, so that if after a while the same guitar is measured again under the same conditions, the results will be practically the same.

The devices used for recording have been a Steinberg USB audio interface UR12 and a Behringer condenser microphone ECM8000. The audio interface provides up to 24-bit resolution and a maximum sampling rate of 192 kHz, which provides the necessary quality for this type of experiment. The microphone used is a condenser microphone with an ultra-flat frequency response from 15 Hz to 20 kHz specially designed for measurement applications.

The recording of the tapping will be made with the guitar with the strings tuned, so that the structure has the same tension as when the instrument is played. To prevent the strings from sounding when tapping, a foam is inserted between the strings and the neck. On a table some marks have been put so that the guitar and the microphone are always at the same distance when recording. The chosen separation distance has been half a meter, and the microphone is positioned pointing to the bridge of the guitar. The guitar is placed vertically at the corresponding mark, on top of a foam that prevents vibrations from being transmitted to the table. In *figure 3* you can see the assembly made for the recording.

Figure 3: Assembly for the recording process

Once everything is in place, the number of taps to be performed is selected in the programme (ten in this case) and tapping is made manually each time the green light is turned on. These taps are applied with a silicone mallet just under the bridge of the guitar, with the maximum possible constancy in the strength and position of the impact. The silicone mallet can be seen in *figure 3*. This is the most important step to improve in the future, to have much more precision in the measures it is necessary to use some device that allows tapping with a constant force in an exact position. The guitar is tapped just below the bridge because it is where it places the centre of the first vibration mode. Tapping there, we are forcing the guitar structure to have maximum amplitude at that point, and therefore the sound produced will have frequency peaks at the resonance frequencies corresponding to this mode.

It is also important to mention that the recordings used in the experiment were not made in a room specially designed for acoustic measurements. For future research, it is recommended that these measurements be performed in a more controlled room to avoid undesirable changes in frequency response due to room resonances.

Regarding the programming of the recording process, as we have said before, GIRAS performs the recording in real time. When the recording process starts, the programme searches for a peak at the microphone input at certain periods of time (in our case, by default, every 0.1 seconds). Peak detection occurs when the input signal exceeds a certain predetermined threshold. When a peak is detected, samples of the following 0.8 seconds are stored, and this signal will be the one that will be analysed. The duration of each impulsive response can be modified according to the needs of the analysis. The analysis of impulsive signals is computed and displayed immediately after each tap, which gives the appearance of real-time measurements. The recordings of this project have been made with a resolution of 24 bits and a sampling frequency of 44100 Hz.

3.2. Calculation of Impulse Response Features

Once the signal has been recorded by GIRAS, immediately after, its spectrum is computed, but only for the first seconds indicated by the user (the first 0.25 seconds by default) and in the chosen frequency range (0 Hz – 1000 Hz by default). The spectrum is

computed doing the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the windowed signal. The window type used in this experiment will be Blackman, but it can be easily changed by the user. The resolution of the FFT will be 65536 samples. Before being used, the signal in frequency is normalized and the mean is made with the rest of recorded taps. Finally, the frequency response is converted to logarithmic scale.

Once we have all the signals that we need, the programme starts to calculate each one of the parameters that we have considered that can be important for the definition of the guitar timbre. In *figure 4* we can see an example of the type of table shown by GIRAS after processing the recorded signals.

FEATURES:	
Feature	Value
T(1,1)_1	98.245 Hz
T(1,1)_2	202.547 Hz
T(1,1)_3	252.342 Hz
Attack Time	8.8481 ms
Decay Time	0.15992 s
Vibration Sensitivity (T1)	-31.2 dB
Vibration Sensitivity (T2)	-30.45 dB
Vibration Sensitivity (T3)	-33.97 dB
Normalized Centroid	0.3632
Low/High ratio	1.1902
Norm. MFCC_4	0.764
Norm. MFCC_6	0.71
Norm. MFCC_12	0.7

Figure 4: Example of the results table shown by GIRAS for one of the guitars used in the experiment

Vibration Modes

There are only three modes of vibration that interest us at the moment, the three modes that are commonly used in guitar construction. To calculate them, in the frequency ranges where each of the modes should appear in the spectrum, we calculate the frequency where the signal has more amplitude, a peak in frequency. The frequency ranges selected are from 80 Hz to 120 Hz for the air mode, 150 Hz to 220 Hz for the soundboard mode and 221 Hz to 270 Hz for the back plate mode. This third mode is computed in a more different way, because the frequency of this mode always has much less amplitude than that of the

other modes. This is due to the fact that tapping is made on the soundboard of the guitar, and therefore the energy that reaches the back plate, and the resonance that this produces, is much lower than the other two. It is probable that the resonance frequency in this mode does not correspond to the maximum of that range. What is done, is to find the peaks that have a certain prominence in the range and calculate which of the peaks has more amplitude. It is probable that some of these frequencies will not be detected well due to a very big mismatch of the resonance frequencies, appearing out of the expected ranges, so it is always recommended to check in the spectrum graph that the calculated frequencies correspond to the peaks of the signal. To be more sure which frequency corresponds to each mode, you can also measure the frequency of the three elements separately, uncoupling the guitar by covering the sound hole and tapping the soundboard and the back plate.

Attack Time

The attack time is the time it takes for the impulsive signal to reach the maximum. For this reason, the calculation is very easy. In the recorded signal, the maximum position is searched, and the time corresponding to that sample will correspond to the attack time.

Decay Time

To calculate the decay time of the impulsive signal it is best to calculate the early decay time, the time it takes to decay 10 dB. Instead of calculating the time it takes to decay from the maximum, we have calculated the time it takes to decay from -10 dB to -20 dB, since it is the most linear part of the time signal. For this purpose, we have run the recorded signal with rectangular windows of 500 samples (11 ms) and a hop proportion of 0.5. In each window we check if the maximum in that signal fragment is lower than -10 dB, and when it is, we save the position of the maximum of that fragment as the second in which the signal is lower than -10 dB. After finding this position, we do the same to find the position where the signal falls below -20 dB. The difference between the seconds we have obtained will be the decay time.

Vibration Sensitivity

To calculate the vibration sensitivity, we have used the formula shown in *figure 1*. The vibration sensitivity is calculated for each of the previously calculated vibration modes. The main problem with this parameter is that we do not have amplitude information, because we are dealing with normalized signals all the time, so the value of the amplitude of the peak used is the normalized value in dB. Using this type of values is possible that the parameter may not be as relevant as it could be if we had accurate amplitude information.

Centroid

To calculate the centroid, our programme first calculates the sum of the amplitudes of the spectrum in the frequency range that we want to calculate it (10000 Hz in our case). Then, sample by sample, the amplitude of all frequencies is summed until the value of half of the total sum of the whole spectrum is reached. The frequency in which this value is reached will be the one that divides the spectrum in two parts with the same energy, the centroid. In order to be able to represent it in the spectrum graph independently of the represented frequency range and to be able to compare it with other measurements more easily, this frequency value is normalized with respect to the maximum frequency of the range with which it has been calculated.

Low-to-High Frequency Ratio

This parameter is very similar to the centroid, but in this case, we set the centre frequency, and divide the total amount of energy left on both sides of the boundary. The ranges we have used for this project are 0 Hz to 400 Hz for low frequencies and 400 Hz to 800 Hz for high frequencies. Summing the amplitude of all the frequencies for each one of the ranges we obtain the total energy for low and for high frequencies, and dividing these two values we would have the LF/HF ratio. The value will always be higher than 1, as there will always be more low frequency content in an impulsive response of this type. The higher the value, the greater the amplitude in the low frequencies than in the high frequencies, and the closer to 1 the closer the energy level between the two types of frequency is.

MFCC

Due to the complexity of the calculation of the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients, and to the fact that it is a bit out of the scope of this project, to calculate the MFCCs with our software, we have used the Matlab function² developed by the Laboratory for the Recognition and Organization of Speech and Audio (LabROSA) of the Columbia University. This function returns an array with 13 MFCC according to the process options that we have indicated inside the function, as 0.025 s of window time, 0.01 s of hop time, 5000 Hz of maximum frequency or the use of 40 warped spectral bands. These values also depend on the amplitude, so we have normalized them with respect to the maximum of them, without taking into account the first two coefficients, which are always much greater than the rest. In the results shown by GIRAS, only those coefficients that have a peak appear, since normally the values tend to decay, but all the coefficients can be visualized pressing the corresponding option in the tools menu. Using this tool, we can also observe in *figure 5* how the graph formed by these coefficients is consistent between each of the taps with which the mean is made.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the MFCC graphs of one of the guitars used in the experiment

² <https://labrosa.ee.columbia.edu/matlab/rastamat/melfcc.m>

3.3. Guitar Timbre Classification Survey

Now that we know how to extract the theoretical characteristics of the guitar timbre, we are going to explain how we have obtained the most subjective data about it. We have asked four guitarists with different profiles to fill out a survey where they are asked to make a ranking with the five classical guitars, according to each of the characteristics of the timbre that we believe that are the most commonly used to define the guitar. This way we will know for each specific characteristic which guitar is the one that contains the most of it and which is the one that contains the least. The characteristics of which we have asked to create a ranking are the same as those defined in the chapter 2.4.: attack, sustain, intelligibility, warmness, balance, volume and dynamic range. Moreover, it has also been asked to fill in a ranking about the personal preference of the guitars in order to know which guitar is normally preferred and therefore which is considered to be of high quality

The survey consists on filling in a table like *table 1*, where all the characteristics appear in rows and the guitars in columns. It was necessary to write inside the five boxes of each of the rows or characteristics, five numbers from 1 to 5 depending on the position of the ranking that each one believes that each guitar deserved. A 1 means that that guitar is the one that has more of that characteristic, and a 5 means that it is the one that has less. There is also a box available to add additional comments on each of the guitars so that the guitarists could add some characteristic that is present in the guitar apart from the proposed ones.

Table 1: Empty table of the timbre survey

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
Attack					
Sustain					
Intelligibility					
Warmness					
Balance					
Volume					
Dynamic Range					
Personal Preference Ranking					
Additional Comments					

The survey was conducted on the 18th of July 2019 at the offices of MIIL. The 5 guitars used in the experiment were provided by the guitarists who participated in it. These guitars were randomly labelled as G1, G2, G3, G4 and G5. In a room, all the guitars were placed in stands so that it would be easy to switch from one guitar to another, as we can see in *figure 6*. One by one the guitarists went to the room, and characteristic by characteristic they played all the guitars until knew clearly the order in which each characteristic is manifested in each guitar. Guitarists were free to play all the guitars as many times as they wanted, and to play in the way that was most comfortable for them to identify and evaluate each characteristic. In addition, there was also freedom in the interpretation of the characteristics, for each one to evaluate according to what each parameter means to them, without being influenced by a previous definition. The survey was carried out before the analysis with GIRAS, so that the results of this did not influence the classification of the guitarists either. The time taken for each of the 4 guitarists to complete the survey was an hour. Completing the survey was a slow process, as for each characteristic the guitarist had to play all the guitars several times. The surveys filled in by each guitarist can be seen in the appendix, in section 8.2.

Figure 6: Guitars used in the project

4. Software Design

In this section we will explain in more detail the way GIRAS-Guitar Impulse Response Analysis Software works. As previously mentioned, this programme has been created in its entirety using Matlab. The interface has been designed with Matlab's app designer tool, and a desktop application has been created with the application compiler. The general appearance of GIRAS can be seen in *figure 7*, where we can see the programme after having recorded one of the guitars of the experiment. As we can observe, the main screen of the programme consists of two graphs, a table of results, and a control panel of different settings.

Figure 7: Screenshot of GIRAS after measuring a guitar

The first graph, which we can see at the top left, is the typical spectrogram, where the frequency is represented in the vertical axis, time in the horizontal axis and colour represents amplitude, being the zones with the warmest colours those of greater amplitude. The frequency range to be represented can be controlled with the slider on the right side of the graph. By default, this range is the first 1000 Hz, which is where most of the relevant information for our type of analysis is found, however, this value can be

changed from 100 Hz to 20000 Hz. This frequency range will also be the one represented in the graph below. On top of the graph, we can find another slider that moves a black line on the time axis. This slider selects the signal fragment to be analysed by the rest of the programme, both for the representation of the following graph and for the computation of all the parameters of the table. By default, a fragment of 0.25 seconds will be selected, as it provides a good representation of the following graph. This graph is computed by making the Fourier transform of the signal recorded in Blackman windows of 7000 samples with a hop of 0.25.

The other graph in the main window represents the frequency spectrum of the impulsive response for the fragment selected above. This is the most important and useful graph when analysing an impulsive response, since in it we can clearly see the peaks of the vibration modes and how the power is distributed in frequency. The discontinuous red line shown in the graph represents the centroid, the point at which the spectrum is divided into two parts of equal power. The most important peaks of the signal, both maximums and minimums are represented by green and red dots respectively, with the value of the frequency in which they are noted on the side. The requirements to be satisfied for a peak to be remarked can be controlled in one of the panels on the right. In it we can control the minimum prominence of the peak, the amplitude limit between the maximum and minimum peaks, the minimum distance between peaks and the minimum width of the peaks. The more restrictive these requirements are, the fewer peaks will be marked. Minimal peaks are also indicated because in some cases there may be a very large drop affecting the sound at those frequencies. If we look at the vibration modes calculated in the features table, we can see that these frequencies normally coincide with the peaks that stand out most in the graph. This graph has been computed by making the Fourier transform of the indicated signal fragment windowed with a single Blackman window of the same size as the fragment.

The recording panel is very simple, you can select the number of taps to record and you can start the recording process. When the record button is pressed, the light of the panel turns green, and each time a tap is detected it turns red and a number is added to the tap counter. When each tap is finished processing and the results are updated, the light turns green and the guitar can be tapped again.

The saving panel consists of a text box, where you write the name with which you want to save the measurement, and two check boxes that allow you to select the formats in which you want to save it, an image with a screenshot or an audio with which you can reload the data into GIRAS. The saved image is a png file with a screenshot with the background changed to white for easy printing. The audio file is a .wav that contains a signal with all the recorded impulses one after the other. When the top menu open option is pressed and one of these files is selected, the audio is loaded as if it were a new recording, and all data is computed again, with the file name appearing directly in the text box.

The preferences option available in the file menu allows us to change several of the default computation settings. In *figure 8* we can see that this new window is composed of 4 panels, one to change the configuration of the representation, another for the configuration of the recording, another to change the limits of the detection of the modes of vibration, and another to change the default values of the filters of the detection of peaks.

Figure 8: Preferences window

In the tools menu we can find some additional options. In it are the options to visualize the graphs of the individual spectrums and of the MFCCs that we have shown previously in *figure 2* and *figure 5* respectively. There is also the option to visualize a cascade graph represented in 3D, widely used in many timbre studies. As we can see in *figure 9*, this graph shows the spectrogram shown in two dimensions in the main window with the amplitude represented in a third axis.

Figure 9: 3D graph of the spectrogram

Finally, we have also added an option to calibrate the microphone, so that every time recordings are made, sound input levels could be set to the same level. In *figure 10* we can see the window created for this option, consisting of a linear gauge and two lights. Each of the lights has a range of amplitude marked on the gauge. When the sound input is within the values of these ranges the light changes from blue to green. The light below indicates if the background noise is at the desired values, and the upper light when tapping the guitar indicates if this tap reaches the correct levels. When calibrating, the input level of the audio interface is first adjusted until the background noise is indicated as correct. After this, by placing the guitar in the measurement position, the guitar is tapped to check if these taps meet the desired levels. If they are not met, a finer adjustment of the input level is made or the force of the tapping is regulated to make them fall within the range.

Figure 10: Microphone calibration window

The general feeling is that we have created a quite easy to use tool with a simple interface that facilitates the analysis of impulsive responses. In addition, the way it is programmed allows new parameter calculations or new functions to be added quite easily, making it an ideal tool for use in research.

5. Results

After collecting the opinion of the four experts about the five guitars available, we can read the results in several ways. First of all is important to clarify that this is a very small-scale experiment. The aim of this experiment is not to draw a definitive conclusion, but rather a first approximation of what parameters may be the most correct for further research into the extraction of timbre features in the future.

In *table 2* we can see the overall results of the guitar ranking according to each of the properties, as a result of adding the individual ratings of the four guitarists who participated in the survey. A 1 means that that guitar is the one that more or better has a specific feature. For example, in the case of the attack or the sustain a 1 means that those guitars are the ones that apparently have longer the time of attack and sustain. In the case of warmness, a 1 means that it is the warmest guitar, with the best lows, and a 5 that is the coldest. The individual evaluations of each of the participants can be consulted in the appendix of the document, in section 10.1., with a brief description of each guitarist's profile.

Table 2: General ranking of the features of different guitars done by guitarists.

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
Attack	2	1	3-4	3-4	5
Sustain	2	3	4-5	1	4-5
Intelligibility	4	5	3	1	2
Warmness	5	4	2	1	3
Balance	5	4	3	1	2
Volume	3	1	5	2	4
Dynamic Range	5	4	3	1	2
Personal Preference Ranking	5	4	3	1	2
Additional Comments	Lack of lows, unbalanced	Many mids, lack of lows, nasal sound	Low sustain	Many mids, lack of brightness	Lack of lows, well-balanced

We can observe that in several characteristics such as warmness, balance or dynamic range, the results are similar to the personal preference ranking of the guitars. It is clear that in these cases these parameters are being affected by the taste of the users. This shows

that the results collected in this survey are influenced to a large extent by the subjectivity of the person carrying it out, although these have tried to be as objective as possible. We can also observe this subjectivity in the fact that the guitar 4 is always ranked in the first positions, while the guitar 1 is always ranked in the last ones. Although thanks to this survey it is clear which guitars are considered of high quality and which of low quality, I don't believe that this quality of the instrument must be directly related to having the same position in the ranking in each of the parameters asked for. To be able to analyse how different the opinions are among the guitarists, we have calculated the standard deviation of the survey in *table 3*.

Table 3: Standard deviation of survey results

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	TOTAL
Attack	1.66	1.80	1.12	1.80	1.73	1.64
Sustain	1.66	1.22	1.80	1.12	0.87	1.38
Intelligibility	1.66	1.50	1.22	2.06	1.50	1.61
Warmness	0.50	0.50	0.87	0.71	1.50	0.89
Balance	0.50	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.12	0.71
Volume	0.50	1.00	0.00	0.50	1.00	0.63
Dynamic Range	0.50	0.71	0.71	0.50	0.71	0.84
Personal Preference Ranking	0.50	0.87	0.87	0.71	1.32	0.89
						1.44

In this *table 3* we can see that the parameters in which the opinions of the different guitarists have differed the most is clearly in the classification of attack, sustain and intelligibility. This has to be because the intelligibility parameter is the most difficult for people to understand, and the attack and sustain each musician has evaluated them playing in a very different way. They checked this parameters playing chords, playing a melody, playing with pick or playing single notes. We can observe that there are two values in which all the participants have coincided, that the guitar 3 is the one that has less volume and that the guitar 4 is the most balanced. Volume has been the feature on which opinions have coincided the most, perhaps because it is the one we are most used to measuring it.

In order to reach a conclusion about which parameters computed by GIRAS can have importance to describe a specific quality of the guitar, we have to consult in *table 4* the

values that GIRAS gives us when we record each one of the guitars. In the appendix of this document, section 10.2., we can find the images generated when saving the recordings of each one of the guitars, where we can observe the spectrums of each one.

Table 4: Results of the analysis of different guitars by GIRAS.

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
T_1 (Hz)	99.591	112.376	86.133	98.245	105.647
T_2 (Hz)	209.949	216.678	196.49	202.547	215.332
T_3 (Hz)	248.978	241.576	242.249	252.342	251.699
Attack Time (ms)	7.6349	7.5125	8.2789	8.8209	9.034
Decay Time (s)	0.20807	0.19813	0.1303	0.15992	0.12102
Vibration Sensitivity (T1) (dB)	-27.94	-29.7	-29.26	-31.2	-29.93
Vibration Sensitivity (T2) (dB)	-30.88	-30.91	-28.21	-30.45	-25.63
Vibration Sensitivity (T3) (dB)	-38.29	-37.72	-41.42	-33.97	-39.03
Normalized Centroid	0.3479	0.3688	0.3659	0.3632	0.395
Low/High Ratio	1.1758	1.1598	1.2208	1.1902	1.2009
Norm. MFCC_4	0.867	0.714		0.764	
Norm. MFCC_6				0.71	
Norm. MFCC_7			0.514		
Norm. MFCC_8	0.135				
Norm. MFCC_9			-0.393		-0.028
Norm. MFCC_10	-0.21		-0.21		
Norm. MFCC_11		-0.605			-0.158
Norm. MFCC_12				0.7	

As we can see, many of the values in *table 4* may be a bit difficult to understand if we are not familiar with them. To make easier the reading of some parameters of *table 4* and to facilitate the comparison with the results of the survey, we have made in *table 5* a ranking of the results of the different guitars for each one of the parameters computed.

Table 5: Ranking of theoretical results of guitar analysis.

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
T_1	3	1	5	4	2
T_2	3	1	5	4	2
T_3	3	5	4	1	2
Attack Time	2	1	3	4	5
Decay Time	1	2	4	3	5
Vibration Sensitivity (T1)	1	3	2	5	4
Vibration Sensitivity (T2)	4	5	2	3	1
Vibration Sensitivity (T3)	3	2	5	1	4
Normalized Centroid	5	2	3	4	1
Low/High Ratio	4	5	1	3	2

If we compare *table 2* with *table 4* or *table 5* we can find relations between the theoretical parameters and the descriptive parameters. The clearest relationship is that of the attack, if we look at the ranking of the attack in *table 2* and the ranking of the attack time in *table 5* we can observe that both match in all positions. As we have said before, we cannot say with certainty that this relationship is always true due to the small number of people and guitars involved in this project, and the large standard deviation of the survey in this parameter, however, in this case it makes a lot of sense that these two parameters match. There has to be a direct relationship between the time that an impulse takes to reach the maximum amplitude and the time that a string takes to do the same on the same guitar.

Concerning sustain, this parameter should be directly related to the decay time, since both terms refer to the time that the sound takes to decay a certain amplitude. This relationship cannot be directly observed in the results, but we can see that the only guitar that has not been placed in the survey in the same order that the theory is the guitar 4. In the overall results of the survey this guitar has been considered the best, while in the theory it is the third guitar with the longest decay time. This change may be due to how the overall quality of the instrument conditions the evaluation of the specific qualities and also, as we said before, the way each musician has checked these parameters. If we look at the individual responses to the survey in the appendix, we can see in *table 9* that the guitarist who performed the sustain analysis counting the time it takes for a single note to expire

is the only one whose ranking matches the theoretical one. Without taking into account the error with the guitar 1 in the survey, we can say that the method used to calculate the decay time is a good way to measure the sustain, but that we should first clarify the ideal methodology to be tested by guitarists.

The descriptive parameters that are related to the timbre as intelligibility, warmness and balance are more complex to find a definition by using theoretical parameters. These parameters are more influenced by the musical tastes of the guitarists, and what they consider a more intelligible sound or a warmer sound. This is the main reason why the results of the survey corresponding to these descriptors are very similar to the personal preference ranking. We cannot reach any conclusion with the theoretical parameters programmed to calculate frequency characteristics as the vibration sensitivity, the centroid or the MFCCs. Although we cannot reach any conclusions from the survey data, the theoretical data can give us a global idea of the quality of the instruments. For example, a considerable difference between guitar 4, which is considered the best guitar by users, and the rest, is that guitar 4 has a very similar vibration sensitivity on all the vibration modes, while on the other guitars there is much more difference between the 3 vibration modes. Also, if we focus on the MFCC, we can see that the guitar 4 is the only one that has three peak coefficients with high values. It is difficult to know how these parameters affect to the final sound, but this could be an important factor in the quality of a guitar. In relation to the centroid, we cannot appreciate any relationship at first glance. Maybe in the case that a guitar was too unbalanced, this value could be relevant. However, in this case we can see in *table 4* how all the values are very similar. However, with the low/high ratio we can find some relationship with the results of the survey. In the *table 4* we can see that guitars 3, 4 and 5 have a much higher ratio than guitars 1 and 2. This means that guitars 3, 4 and 5 are the ones that have greater power difference between low and high frequencies. This, besides coinciding more or less with the results of the survey in terms of warmness and balance, also coincides with the additional comments made by the guitarists, who generally commented that guitar 1 and 2 were the worst timbre and those with the least lows, and that guitar 3, 4 and 5 were well balanced.

For parameters related to amplitude such as volume and dynamic range, we have not been able to develop any function to try to calculate them, because we cannot ensure that a greater amplitude is not due to a greater force in the recorded impacts. However, we found

a theoretical parameter of the calculated ones that seems to have a lot of relation with the volume perceived by the guitarists. Guitars with higher frequency in the vibration modes seem to be related to a higher perceived volume.

Despite all the parameters that we have calculated to try to define the timbre, the most important and what most defines the timbre of the guitar are the parameters that have always been measured traditionally, the vibration modes. A good tuning of the three vibration modes corresponding to the air (T_1), the soundboard (T_2) and the back plate (T_3) is essential for a good quality instrument. According to Gore, T. & Gilet, G. for classical guitars the vibration modes have to appear between 95 Hz and 107 Hz for T_1, between 180 Hz and 202 Hz for T_2, and between 226 Hz and 254 Hz for T_3 [2]. If we observe the values of these parameters in the guitars used we can see that the only guitar that has the three frequencies within the range is the guitar 4, which the guitarists have clearly chosen as the best guitar. The guitar 2 is the only one that only has one of the frequencies within the range, being this the one of the back plate, that is the one that has less importance in the sound of the instrument. This mismatch of the vibration modes has resulted in the musicians choosing this guitar as one of the worst. The other three guitars have one of the modes out of range, however, only the guitar 3 has the soundboard mode within the range, being this the most important of the three vibration modes. Then, if we try to make a ranking taking into account the adjustment of the vibration modes of the guitars, it would be as shown in *table 6*. This order makes sense with the results of the survey, this matches a lot with both the personal preference ranking and the timbre descriptors such as intelligibility, warmth and balance.

Table 6: Ranking according to the adjustment of the resonance modes.

G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
3-4	5	2	1	3-4

Finally, if we focus now on the additional comments made to each of the guitars we will see that some of this can be explained with the theoretical data. Guitars 1, 2 and 5 have received the comment that the sound lacks low frequencies. These guitars are exactly the three that have the vibration mode of the soundboard above the recommended range, so the resulting sound will have more high-frequency than low-frequency content. Guitar 3

was commented as having poor sustain, which is true if we check with the decay time in *table 4*.

As we have seen, all the conclusions drawn with these results are assumptions made with the few data available. A much more extensive experiment would be needed in order to draw definitive conclusions. These results may serve as a basis for further research and for adding improvements to the software to obtain better results.

6. Conclusions and future work

As a conclusion to this project, we can say that we have developed a software that facilitates the analysis of the impulsive response of the guitar. GIRAS allows you to record and observe the spectrum immediately, in addition to displaying peak frequencies on the graph and other spectrum information that may be relevant, saving much more time than with other applications of the same type. This tool fits perfectly to the needs that the MIIL company had at the beginning of the project. A tool easy to use without much technical knowledge and with a relatively cheap infrastructure. In addition to helping MIIL or any luthier to understand and design guitars, GIRAS also makes it easier for researchers to add new functions that calculate new physical parameters that can help to better understand the timbre of the guitar. It is completely adjustable, at any time, you can change the settings with which the analysis is being performed to adapt it more to your needs. Moreover, it satisfies one of the biggest problems with this type of measurements, the analysis is reproducible if it is done with the same setup. If you perform an analysis of the same guitar at two different times, you will get almost the same results.

With regard to the timbre features extraction, as we have repeated several times during the previous chapter, we cannot fully assure that there is a direct relationship between any of the calculated parameters and the sound perceived by the user. However, this uncertainty is not only due to the fact of having done the survey with very few people and guitars, it is also due to the way each person interprets each sound. Not all people hear all the sounds equally, there are a lot of factors that influence the way each person interpret each different sound. This is why even if the experiment had been done on a greater scale, this differences between the evaluations would have kept appearing.

Overlooking these problems, we have found parameters that we believe are being calculated in the right way, such as attack and decay time and the low/high ratio. The first two are directly related to the attack time and sustain of the guitar, while the low/high ratio we need more measures to be able to decide if it is more related to the warmth or to the balance, although the two are related to each other. Other parameters like vibration modes and MFCC, require a more specific study to learn how the relationship between the different frequencies or coefficients affects the final sound of the guitar. The vibration

sensitivity and the centroid surely need a readjustment in the way of calculation and a larger scale experiment before discarding its influence on the timbre of the guitar. In addition to improving the functions already created, it is also necessary to add new functions that allow us to have more options to find a relationship with the timbre. For example, the calculation of the spectral tilt, which can allow us to measure the level of the energy drop from the low frequencies to the high frequencies.

One of the main ways to improve the operation of GIRAS and obtain better results, is to add an amplitude control to stop having all values normalized. In this way, we could calculate new parameters related to the volume of the instrument and improve the calculation of others such as the vibration sensitivity, which depends on the amplitude of the peaks. To control the amplitude of impulsive signals, it would be necessary to improve the way these signals are recorded using more modern techniques such as the use of impulsive hammers, shakers or MLS signals that allows to measure the strength of the impulses. In addition, another important factor would be to carry out the measurements in an acoustically controlled room, avoiding that the resonances of the room affect the vibration of the musical instrument.

Another function that would help to improve GIRAS, would be to add the option of calculating the resonance frequencies of the soundboard and the back plate decoupled, so that when recording the response of the coupled system, the vibration modes corresponding to each of the elements can be detected more accurately.

The incorporation of a database into the software will be essential to improve possible future research. A database that allows to store all the data computed by GIRAS as well as to add parameters about the construction properties of each guitar model analysed. In this way it will be possible to monitor how changes in construction affect acoustic characteristics. In addition, the use of this tool in instrument manufacturing companies such as MIIL will allow obtaining a large database in a short time period, which can be used in future research to make a more extensive study of the guitar timbre and its features. One of the possible uses of this database can be the use of the data to train a machine learning algorithm, which allows us to relate the theoretical data with the final sound of the guitar. Using this technique, many data that at first sight do not give us any

information about the timbre, such as the MFCC, can end up being essential when classifying a guitar.

Finally, in order to improve the identification and definition of the terms used by guitarists to describe their instrument, the experiment carried out should be improved. First of all, it would be necessary to increase the magnitude of the project, involving many more guitarists and many more guitar models, although we have already said that there is a personal factor in the way the people interpret the sound that we cannot control. The guitars used should not be those belonging to the participants of the experiment themselves, as it is very probable that the guitarist will choose his guitar as the best in many cases. All guitars should have the same type of strings so that they influence in the same way in all models. The tests should be done blindly, so that the guitarist does not know which guitar is being played. In this way we will avoid the influence of factors such as aesthetics, the brand or always choosing the guitar that has liked the most from the beginning. Another very good option for a future new experiment, would be that a single guitarist plays the instrument and the rest of the guitarists perform the evaluation at the same time, listening to exactly the same sound. In this way, we will avoid the influence of the way each musician plays the guitar and the fact that each one has a particular way of measuring each parameter. For this, also it will be necessary to define previously the specific meaning of each one of the parameters to identify, to avoid that each one understands different concepts.

In general, we can say that this project has helped to lay the foundations that MIIL company will use on future research about guitar timbre. We have developed a very good software that will facilitate this type of research, as we have demonstrated in this master thesis. We expect that with the passage of time this tool will become more and more precise and can be used to define the acoustic qualities of a guitar just by measuring its impulsive response. Above all, we hope that the work done here, could help to create innovative musical instruments with a great acoustic quality.

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10. Appendix

10.1. Individual answers to guitar classification

Table 7: Ranking of guitars for guitarist 1

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
Attack	1	3	2	5	4
Sustain	5	2	4	1	3
Intelligibility	3	5	2	1	4
Warmness	4	3	1	2	5
Balance	4	5	2	1	3
Volume	3	1	5	2	4
Dynamic Range	5	4	3	1	2
Personal Preference Ranking	5	3	2	1	4
Additional Comments					
Guitarist Profile	Young guitarist specialized in classical music with education in music school				

Table 8: Ranking of guitars for guitarist 2

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
Attack	2	1	3	5	4
Sustain	2	3	5	1	4
Intelligibility	1	3	2	5	4
Warmness	5	4	3	1	2
Balance	5	3	4	1	2
Volume	3	1	5	2	4
Dynamic Range	5	3	4	1	2
Personal Preference Ranking	4	5	3	2	1
Additional comments	Lack of lows and unbalanced	Nasal sound	Low sustain	Lack of brightness	Well-balanced
Guitarist Profile	Experienced musician in various instruments and musical styles with many years of experience testing different guitar models.				

Table 9: Ranking of guitars for guitarist 3

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
Attack	5	4	3	1	2
Sustain	1	2	5	3	4
Intelligibility	4	3	5	2	1
Warmness	5	4	3	2	1
Balance	5	3	4	1	2
Volume	4	3	5	1	2
Dynamic Range	4	5	3	2	1
Personal Preference Ranking	5	3	4	2	1
Additional comments	Lack of lows	Many mids		Many mids	
Guitarist Profile	Musician with great experience playing all kinds of musical instruments such as drums, piano, bass, electric guitar or acoustic guitar.				

Table 10: Ranking of guitars for guitarist 4

	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
Attack	3	1	5	2	4
Sustain	3	5	1	2	4
Intelligibility	5	4	3	1	2
Warmness	5	4	2	1	3
Balance	5	3	2	1	4
Volume	3	1	5	2	4
Dynamic Range	5	4	2	1	3
Personal Preference Ranking	5	4	2	1	3
Additional comments	Lack of lows	Lack of lows			Lack of lows
Guitarist Profile	Guitar luthier and guitarist, with high knowledge on guitar timbre				

10.2. Results of the guitar analysis by GIRAS

In the following link can be downloaded the audio files and high quality images saved when making the measurement of each guitar with GIRAS:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1zbDPMa3h4HZPprmV-OZM68LA7fgK0V6A>

The configuration used to obtain these results has been the one we have established by default and can be seen in *figure 8*.

Figure 11: Result of the analysis of the guitar 1

Figure 12: Result of the analysis of the guitar 2

Figure 13: Result of the analysis of the guitar 3

Figure 14: Result of the analysis of the guitar 4

Figure 15: Result of the analysis of the guitar 5